

3 070 cm^{-1} due to 2-aminopyrimidyl mode⁶ and a strong band at 1 630–1 655 cm^{-1} due to $\delta_{\text{NH}} + \nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}} + \nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ ⁷ have been observed. These bands suggest the presence of pyrimidine ring in the compounds. A weak band at 1 500–1 530 cm^{-1} assigned to $\text{NH} + (\text{C}=\text{S}) + \text{NCS}$ deformation, a weak band at 1 410–1 435 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu_{\text{NH}} + \nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}} + \nu_{\text{NCN}}$, a weak band at 1 300–1 320 cm^{-1} assigned to $\delta_s(\text{NH} + \text{CH}_3)$ mode⁷, a medium intensity band at 1 200–1 270 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}} + \nu_{\text{NCN}}$ have been observed. A peak of medium intensity at 1 015–1 050 cm^{-1} has been assigned to the vibrational ($\text{N}-\text{C}-\text{N}$ -rock) + ($\text{N}-\text{C}-\text{N} + \text{C}=\text{S}$)⁸ and an intense band at 700–720 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}} + \nu_{\text{NCS}}$ ⁹. A strong band at 600–650 cm^{-1} assigned to δ_{CH} ⁸, a strong band at 530–560 cm^{-1} assigned to δ_{NCS} and a band of moderate intensity at 420–460 cm^{-1} assigned to NCS bending have been observed. All these peaks suggest the most probable structures of the thiocarbamides.

Antifungal activity: Antifungal activity of the compounds was tested by standard spore germination inhibition method¹⁰ against two fungi *Colletotrichum falcatum* and *Alternaria brassicae* causing major diseases of sugarcane and *Brassica* group of crops, respectively. It was observed that compounds 6–9, 12, 13, 15–18 were highly toxic against *C. falcatum* and compounds 13, 15–18 were toxic against *A. brassicae*.

Nematicidal activity: Nematicidal activity of the compounds was tested at different dilutions against two important nematode pests *Meloidogyne javanica* and *Anguina tritici*. Observations on mortality were recorded by counting the living and dead second stage larvae under stereoscopic microscope. Compounds 2, 9, 13, 16–18 were highly effective against *M. javanica* and compounds 1, 7, 8 and 14 were effective against *A. tritici*.

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Preparation of 2-[N⁴-{N¹-(2'-Thiazolyl)sulphanilamido}] -4-(4'-bromoanilino)-6-(substituted-phenylthioureido)-s-triazine and Study of their Antibacterial Activity

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SEVERAL related 2-[N⁴-{N¹-(2'-thiazolyl)sulphanilamido}] -4-(4'-bromoanilino)-6-(substituted-phenylthioureido)-s-triazine (1), where the substitution R = phenyl, *o*-tolyl, *m*-tolyl, *p*-tolyl, *o*-nitrophenyl, *m*-nitrophenyl, *p*-nitrophenyl, *o*-chlorophenyl, *p*-chlorophenyl, have been prepared in view of the fact that a number of related compounds are known to have biological activities¹.

N¹-2-Thiazolylsulphanilamide was condensed with cyanuric chloride to give 2-[N⁴-{N¹-(2'-thiazolyl)sulphanilamido}] -4,6-dichloro *s*-triazine, which when condensed with *p*-bromoaniline gave 2-[N⁴-{N¹-(2'-thiazolylsulphanilamido}] -4-(4'-bromoanilino)-6-chloro-*s*-triazine, and the latter on reaction with various phenylthioureas yield the compound of the type (1).

Experimental

Infrared spectra of the compounds were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

2-N⁴-{N¹-(2'-Thiazolyl)sulphanilamido}] -4,6-dichloro-*s*-triazine : N¹-2-Thiazolylsulphanilamide (0.05 mol, 12.75 g) dissolved in acetone was added in a well stirred solution of cyanuric chloride (0.05

mol, 9.25 g) dissolved in acetone, and the temperature maintained at 0–5°. The mixture was adjusted to pH 6–7 and stirred for 2 h. The content was then poured on crushed ice, filtered, and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from 95% ethanol, (80%), m.p. 350°.

2-[N⁴-{N¹-(2'-Thiazolyl)sulphanilamido}] -4-(4'-bromoanilino)-6-chloro-s-triazine : *p*-Bromoaniline (0.01 mol, 1.72 g) dissolved in acetone was added dropwise during 1.5 h to a mechanically stirred solution of 2-[N⁴-{N¹-(2'-thiazolyl)sulphanilamido}] -4,6-dichloro-s-triazine (0.01 mol, 4.03 g) in acetone at 35°. The temperature was gradually increased 45° during 2 h and pH maintained at 7 by aqueous sodium carbonate solution. The reaction mixture was then cooled to room temperature. It was poured in crushed ice and 2% HCl added. The resulting solid was filtered, dried and crystallised from 95% ethanol, (70%), m.p. > 350°.

General method for preparation of 2-[N⁴-{N¹-(2'-thiazolyl)sulphanilamido}] -4-(4'-bromoanilino)-6-(substituted-phenylthioureido)-s-triazine : 2-[N⁴-{N¹-(2'-Thiazolyl)sulphanilamido}] -4-(4'-bromoanilino)-6-chloro-s-triazine (0.01 mol, 5.4 g) in acetone and various phenylthiourea (0.01 mol) in acetone at pH 7 were refluxed for 3 h at 80–90° on a water-bath. The mixture was cooled to room temperature and then poured on crushed ice and filtered. The resulting solid was crystallised from 95% ethanol.

The yield varied from 50 to 65%; m.p. of the compounds : R = phenyl, 139°; *o*-tolyl, 198°; *m*-tolyl, 165°; *p*-tolyl, 166°; *o*-nitrophenyl, 120°; *m*-nitrophenyl, 158°; *p*-nitrophenyl, 190°; *o*-chlorophenyl, 218°; *p*-chlorophenyl, 173°.

Antibacterial activity : The compounds were screened for antibacterial activity using paper-disc or agar-diffusion technique² in acetone solution. The bacteria taken for the study were *Staphylococcus aureus* (gram-positive) and *Escherichia coli* (gram-negative).

In case of *E. coli*, the maximum zone of inhibition was found for 2-[N⁴-{N¹-(2'-thiazolyl)sulphanilamido}] -4-(4'-bromoanilino)-6-(2'-chlorophenylthioureido)-s-triazine (2.0 mm) and the minimum zone of inhibition for 2-[N⁴-{N¹-(2'-thiazolyl)sulphanilamido}] -4-(4'-bromoanilino)-6-(4'-methylphenylthioureido)-s-triazine (0.5 mm). In case of *S. aureus*, the maximum zone of inhibition was found for 2-[N⁴-{N¹-(2'-thiazolyl)sulphanilamido}] -4-(4'-bromoanilino)-6-(2'-chlorophenylthioureido)-s-triazine (1.5 mm) and the minimum zone of inhibition for 2-[N⁴-{N¹-(2'-thiazolyl)sulphanilamido}] -4-(4'-bromoanilino)-6-(4'-methylphenylthioureido)-s-triazine and 2-[N⁴-{N¹-(2'-thiazolyl)sulphanilamido}] -4-(4'-bromoanilino)-6-(4'-chlorophenylthioureido)-s-triazine (0.5 mm).

All the compounds in general recorded the following ir bands : 860–830 (C₃N₃), 1580–1570 (NH), 1160–1140 (C=S), 1560–1520 (NHCSNH) and 1130–1100 cm⁻¹ (SO₂NH).

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A New Aliphatic Constituent of *Melastoma malabathricum* Linn.†

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THE leaves and flowers of *Melastoma malabathricum* Linn.^{1,2} (Melastomaceae), a shrub of variable heights, are used in folk medicine.

The investigation on the leaves and flowers of *M. malabathricum* resulted in the isolation of a number of compounds. We report here the isolation of a new alcoholic constituent Mm₁, and its characterisation as 32-methyl-1-tritriacontanol along with some known compounds.

The petrol (b.p. 60–80°) extract of the air-dried finely powdered leaves (3 kg) on chromatography (silica gel, 60–120 mesh; eluant: petrol-benzene, 1:1) yielded β-sitosterol, the identity of which was confirmed by m.m.p. and superimposable ir spectra with an authentic sample.

The petrol extract afforded the new aliphatic alcohol, Mm₁ (eluant: benzene-ethyl acetate, 4:1). Compound Mm₁ (0.002%), C₃₄H₇₀O (M⁺494), white crystals (petrol-chloroform), m.p. 76–8°, was neutral to litmus, soluble in chloroform, benzene and sparingly soluble in petroleum ether. The compound did not show any high intensity absorption maxima in the uv region, but showed ir absorption maxima characteristic of an aliphatic primary alcohol at ν_{max} (KBr) 3445 (m, primary OH), 2920, 2840 (s, alkane CH₂ stretch), 1385 (s), 1360 (m, gem-dimethyl), 1050 (br, m), 720 and 710 cm⁻¹. ¹H nmr spectrum (200 MHz) showed the signals in conformity with the proposed structure of an aliphatic alcohol. The ¹H nmr signals were observed at δ (CDCl₃) 0.91 (3H, s, CH₃), 0.93 (3H, s,

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